

RESEARCH ON THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' NATIONAL CULTURE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Erjanova Venera Kuanishbaevna

Assistant Teacher of departments of pedagogical psychology, Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This thesis describes the results of research on the formation of national culture of students in higher education institutions.

Key words: higher education institution, student, ideology, idea, education, education.

When it comes to national education, the well-known educationist A. Avloni's profound words, "Education is a matter of life or death, or salvation, or destruction, or happiness, or disaster" involuntarily attract people's attention. This is stated in Article 63 of Chapter 14 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "The family is the main link of society and has the right to be under the protection of society and the state." Family-ideological education is one of the most important social factors. Because the family is the basis of society and has strong spiritual foundations of many centuries. The formation of students and young people in the family and the influence of traditions and customs specific to national values on young people in the family is one of the strengths of opportunities. Students who have formed spiritual and moral education understand the responsibility of their profession and tasks such as maintaining the peace of society. Highly moral pedagogues educate their students to be humane, patriotic, morally pure, educated, humble and noble. Spirituality is an internal positive, spiritual factor that determines the strength, development, opportunities and prospects of an individual, nation, state and society.

In the process of education, the issue of ideological education is of particular importance. That's why ideological education is a variety of education in the family, preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special education, higher education institutions, neighborhood, social and public institutions, administrative and political organizations, labor teams. carried out by using glue tools.

"Ideological education refers to the process of purposeful formation of philosophical, political, legal, religious, aesthetic, ethical, artistic, professional and other principles in the mind and thinking system of people based on a specific ideology." So, to what extent is ideological education being delivered to young people in our country today? In this regard, parents

To what extent are the responsibilities of teachers-coaches and others manifested? Unfortunately, we have to admit that in some cases indifference prevails and insufficient attention is paid to ideological education. For example, in some families, parents are involved in the ideological upbringing of children their knowledge is insufficient. How can a parent who does not have enough political, legal, religious, aesthetic, moral knowledge be an example to his child? It is necessary to establish a practical education that inculcates the national ideology in the minds of young people. So, the national ideology clearly relies on a socio-pedagogical, socio-psychological mechanism - ideological education. Ideological education is a scientific program of spiritual restoration of this nation, raising it as a whole, ensuring its spiritual, political and social activity.

It is known that the minds of young people are in the process of formation, and they are easily influenced by various ideas (including destructive ones). They also have a keen sense of emotional intelligence and are more aware of situations where there is a disparity between words and actions. Any injustices that are philosophically accepted by adults can cause severe damage to the youth's not yet fully formed mind and worldview. Ideological education prevents this. Ideological education is a process aimed at forming the worldview of a person, social group, nation, society, arming them with ideological knowledge that expresses their specific goals.

Ideological education and ideological education are inseparable parts of each other. Collaborative activities of various social institutions and systematic and gradual way only as a result of ideological education, the complex and exciting process of inculcating certain ideas into people's minds and hearts gives the intended result.

In particular, social institutions such as science, culture, cultural and educational institutions, family, labor teams, political parties, non-governmental organizations, mass media occupy an important place in this process. This place is, on the one hand, that each of them has its own and unique ways of influencing the minds of people, and, on the other hand, that every person is under the regular influence of these institutions throughout his life or at a certain stage of it. is determined by being A person's development in life is determined by the society, its priority views and values, their assimilation and strengthening. depends on the educational system that serves. We talked briefly about the family above. Now let's think about the educational system, which is one of the main institutions.

After all, a human child learns the social experience and values accumulated in educational institutions on a scientific basis and in a systematic way. Due to the interdependence between the stages of the educational system, gradualism in the process of ideological education is ensured. As a result, the scope of human knowledge is enriched both quantitatively and qualitatively. It should also be noted that conceptual knowledge is directly and directly assimilated in the educational process itself. There is also an opportunity to directly check the results of ideological propaganda in the educational system and to constantly improve it. This task, of course, falls on the teachers and coaches. The process of ideological and ideological education of young people is carried out together with the educational process. In this case, it is necessary to inculcate the national idea and ideology in other fields of science as well, not only in the sciences that are part of the national idea. However, from the teachers who teach from the national idea series, through the following, that is, to increase the quality of teaching, first of all, in the course of the lesson, the formation of qualities such as independence, initiative, sense of responsibility and critical thinking of each pupil-student, and science it is carried out by the teacher's scientific potential, professional skills, and the ability to use non-traditional methods of teaching. Such person-oriented aspects of education lead to a solid mastery of the subject by the student, a deep understanding of the goals and tasks of the subject. After all, the application of interactive methods that meet today's demands in the teaching process encourages students to make decisions independently, freely choose assignments, and create. This process requires experience, knowledge, persuasiveness, speech, self-confidence and other such active pedagogical qualities from the teacher.

The main work method of the teacher, based on the knowledge, understanding, and ideas he has, is first of all to form strong beliefs in the minds of students and young people, and to influence them.

That's why the teacher gets the honorable name "coach". "In the course of his work, the coach helped young people to decide on a healthy lifestyle, to help boys and girls grow up to be physically strong, mature individuals in all respects, from the problems of alcoholism and drug addiction, it is necessary to protect against religious and extremist influences, to explain the negative consequences of the attacks of "mass culture", a group of philosophers says.

Coaches should be able to form the following in the spiritual image of young people:

- independent thinker, master of modern sciences and professions, devoted to his country, his people, able to continue the work started by the elderly and middle generation, healthy in all respects...;
- I will contribute to the development of my homeland, ready to go out on the field with a tight waist, determined and energetic;
- able to work on a computer, learn English and other languages, compete with peers in foreign countries;
- who never gets tired of learning;
- who is not inferior to anyone else in any field, who thinks in a new way;
- his eyes light up, his actions and aspirations are so determined and bold, he lives with pride saying, "give me a chance, I will show myself";
- who devotes himself to work with all his being, believes in tomorrow and works diligently;
- who never gets tired of studying;
- physically and mentally healthy;
- who closely connects his life and destiny with our mother Uzbekistan and confidently strives for the future;
- determined, bright-eyed, with modern knowledge and skills, able to compete with peers on the world stage;
- highly cultured, deeply immersed in the world of world art, fully aware of its secrets, the immortal heritage of great music creators;
- not deceived by various deceptions, false promises, fake and false information;
- has modern knowledge and thinking, a healthy outlook;
- who says that we will build our tomorrow with our own hands;
- who will be stronger, more educated, smarter, wiser and certainly happier than us;
- has the feeling of loving one's country and living passionately for it;
- an active participant, not a distant observer of large-scale renovations, construction and beautification works;
- well-versed in the past history of his people;
- looking around with open eyes, making conclusions, having his own independent opinion, always living inspired by the truth;
- he lives with his head held high, relying only on his own strength and potential;
- a highly qualified professional capable of taking responsibility for the future and development of his country;

- stable in a healthy way of life, free from drug addiction, immorality, all kinds of harmful influences coming from outside, threats and dangers under the guise of "popular culture";
- seeker of intellectual knowledge, intellectual wealth;
- not saying "when the time we want will come, then we will achieve our goal", but devoting knowledge and energy for a bright future like his ancestors and contemporaries;
- who understands well who is the descendant of what great people, what kind of spiritual legacy they are;
- a person who is ready to sacrifice himself for his parents, children, country, Motherland
- Strive to become a true child of the nation and achieve it.

In short, upbringing and education can never be separated from each other. Only when these two processes are organized on a harmonious, continuous basis, a modern profession with decent, moral qualities, high spirituality, at the same time knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy, with a broad outlook and thinking. - educates patriotic students who are masters of the profession.

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